

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

The limits of the metapopulation: Lineage fragmentation in a widespread terrestrial salamander
(Plethodon cinereus)

Brian P. Waldron; Emily F. Watts; Donald J. Morgan; Maggie M. Hantak; Alan R. Lemmon;
Emily Moriarty Lemmon; Shawn R. Kuchta

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FIGURE S1. Map of localities with morphological data available depicted orange points. Also shown are the 107 localities sequenced for mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) from Radomski et al. (2020), which were used to inform the subset of localities sequenced for anchored hybrid enrichment (AHE), and also provided mtDNA sequence data if AHE data were unavailable in the present study. For comparative analyses, all localities with morphological data were assigned to a nearby site that had mtDNA or both AHE and mtDNA data available. The exceptions are the cluster of localities between populations 104 and 106, on the southern Delmarva Peninsula, which were not included in PGLS.

FIGURE S2. Evaluation of K values for STRUCTURE analysis of 38 samples, interpreted using the ‘pophelper’ R package: a) Log-likelihood of the data; b) Rate of change of the likelihood distribution; c) Absolute value of the second-order rate of change of the likelihood; d) ΔK .

FIGURE S3. Population clustering assignments for STRUCTION (comparing $K = 2$ and $K = 5$) and DAPC ($K = 5$). The STRUCTION results of $K = 5$ match pie charts depicted in Fig. 1a,b. The lower horizontal axis labelled “mt” indicates the mtDNA clade of the samples above.

FIGURE S4. Population clustering assignments for STRUCTION, with values $K = 6 - 10$.

FIGURE S5. Population substructure within four genomic groups inferred using STRUCTURE, after excluding admixed samples. Group 1 was not analyzed because it included only one sample. For each group, ‘pophelper’ results evaluating solutions for K are shown, matching panel information in Fig. S2. Both $K = 5$ and $K = 2$ are illustrated for Group 4, along with a horizontal axis depicting the mtDNA clade of these samples. Although $K = 5$ was best supported for the substructure, $K = 2$ is also shown for comparison with the Ohio (OH) and Pennsylvania (PA) mtDNA clades.

FIGURE S6. Cross-validation predictive accuracy of conStruct models, comparing the spatial (blue) and non-spatial (green) models for each value of K. Error bars represent standard errors across 10 replicate runs.

FIGURE S7. Admixture coefficients from spatial models fit using conStruct for values of $K = 2$ to 6.

FIGURE S8. Estimated effective migration surface from FEEMS. Warmer colors (red) represent areas in which effective migration is lower than expected under IBD, while cooler colors (blue) represent greater migration than expected.

FIGURE S10. Concatenated mtDNA and AHE phylogenies estimated using BEAST2, a) including and b) excluding admixed populations, for samples with morphological data available for the population. See Table S2 for sample names corresponding to population numbers.

FIGURE S11. Species tree estimated using ASTRAL, excluding admixed samples. Node values represent local posterior probabilities (*left*) and concordance factors (*right*; represented as a proportion).

a)

b)

c)

FIGURE S12. Evaluation of the number of migration events to include in TreeMix using the optM R package: a) Analysis including 28 samples after dropping admixed individuals, with each sample represented as a tip; b) Analysis including all samples, with each sample represented as a tip, including admixed samples; c) Analysis including five genomic groups, with samples first assigned to their genomic group.

FIGURE S13. TreeMix analyses: a) Analysis including 28 samples after dropping admixed individuals, with each sample represented as a tip. One migration event. b) Analysis including all samples, with each sample represented as a tip, including admixed samples. One migration event; c) Analysis including all samples, with each sample represented as a tip, including admixed samples. Two migration events; d) Analysis including five genomic groups, with samples first assigned to their genomic group. One migration event.

FIGURE S14. SNaQ network scores for increasing numbers of reticulation events (h_{\max}) allowed in the network. Lower network scores indicate a better fit to the data.

FIGURE S15. Principal components analysis (PCA) of morphological measurements for all adult *P. cinereus* (>32 mm snout-vent length; SVL): a) trunk length was included in the analysis, and b) trunk length was excluded and all variables were divided by SVL to correct for differences in overall body size. For both analyses, 95% confidence ellipses are drawn around means of genomic groups, with group colors matching those from the main text (e.g. Fig 1a,b). Samples that are admixed are assigned to a unique group according to the admixed genotype (e.g. “4&5” are samples at localities admixed between Groups 4 and 5 according to STRUCTURE).

FIGURE S16. Evaluation of the number of clusters estimated using SuperSOM. The Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and sampling frequency suggested approximately $K = 3$ groups.

FIGURE S17. Map of “species coefficients” for each sample in the SuperSOM analysis. Three primary clusters were inferred; an additional cluster is visible for $K = 4$ (“D”), represented in low frequency in southeastern populations.

FIGURE S18. Variable importance (codebook vectors) for input layers and variables in the SuperSOM analysis.

FIGURE S19. *Gdi* values using the dataset using multiple samples per genomic group, but excluding admixed samples, using an alternate topology to estimate parameters: (*P. serratus*; (Group 3; ((Group 2; Group 1); (Group 4; Group 5)))). See Extended Materials and Methods.

FIGURE S20. *Gdi* values for 10 replicate datasets in which a single, non-admixed sample was randomly selected to represent each group for parameter estimation in BPP. See Extended Materials and Methods.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

TABLE S1. See attached Excel file. Anchored hybrid enrichment sample data.

TABLE S2. See attached Excel file. Morphology sampling locality data.

TABLE S3. See attached Excel file. Anchored hybrid enrichment locus summary statistics.

TABLE S4. See attached Excel file. Bayesian Phylogenetics and Phylogeography (BPP) parameter estimates.

TABLE S5. See attached Excel file. Morphology principal components analysis (PCA) loadings.

TABLE S6. See attached Excel file. Morphology permutation test pairwise *P*-values.

TABLE S7. See attached Excel file. Morphology PGLS models and results.

EXTENDED MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling and Anchored Hybrid Enrichment

We selected 38 individuals of *P. cinereus* (Fig. 1a,b; Supplementary Table S1), each representing a locality sequenced for mtDNA from Radomski et al (2020), to sequence using anchored hybrid enrichment (AHE) at the Center for Anchored Phylogenomics at Florida State University (Lemmon et al. 2012). These samples represent an informed subset of the known phylogeographic diversity based on allozymes and mtDNA (Supplementary Fig. S1) (Highton and Webster 1976; Radomski et al. 2020). We made an effort to include samples within the core range of each clade, as well as areas of potential secondary contact between clades to detect admixture. The same population numbers from Radomski et al. (2020) are retained here to facilitate comparisons between the two studies. For clarity, we refer to clade names when referring to the mtDNA clades identified in Radomski et al. (2020), “genomic groups” for groups identified with AHE in the present study, and “populations” as synonymous with localities. We also included three samples of *P. serratus* from the southern Appalachian region as an outgroup for some analyses.

Preparation of AHE loci followed Lemmon et al. (2012). Briefly, DNA for *P. cinereus*, *P. serratus*, and 25 other species of *Plethodon* that are the subjects of ongoing studies was extracted using Qiagen DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit (Qiagen). Samples were standardized to ~20 ng/μL, and fragmented to ~300 base pairs (bp) using a Covaris E220 focused ultra-sonicator (Covaris, Inc., Woburn, MA, USA). Samples were indexed, pooled, and enriched using an Agilent Custom SureSelect kit, and sequenced using an Illumina HiSeq 2000 (Lemmon et al. 2012). Data were processed using scripts and same methodology as in Prum et al. (2015), Pyron et al. (2016), and Booker et al. (2022) except where noted. Briefly, overlapping reads were merged (‘Merge.java’)

and assembled, ('Assembler.java') (Prum et al. 2015), and alleles were phased in a Bayesian framework using read overlap information using 'Allelephaser.jar' (Pyron et al. 2016; Booker et al. 2022). We filtered for low-level contaminants ('GatherALLConSeqsWithOKCoverage.java') and performed an initial assessment of orthology based on pairwise distances for each locus ('GetPairwiseDistanceMeasures.java'). Sequences were aligned using MAFFT (Kato and Standley 2013) and trimmed and masked to remove sites with excessive missing data following the procedure and parameters used in Pyron et al. (2016) ('TrimAndMaskRawAlignments.java'). Sites present in over 50% of samples were considered good sites, sites were masked if they contained fewer than 14 good sites within 20 bp windows, and sites with over 22 masked or missing bases were removed (Pyron et al. 2016). Our initial filtering procedure yielded 351 loci across all *Plethodon*, and we extracted the samples of *P. cinereus* and *P. serratus* for further analyses.

We flagged additional potentially paralogous loci within *P. cinereus* by calculating the pairwise HKY distance of each individual's two phased alleles using ape in R 4.1.2 (Paradis and Schliep 2019; R Core Team 2021), taking the average value for each locus. Loci with outlier values (using the 'boxplot' function in R; $N = 20$) were inspected and excluded, leaving $N = 331$ loci. With further visual inspection of phased sequence alignments and gene trees (see below), we identified some loci that contained interior regions in which all or most individuals (> 0.75) in our dataset were identically heterozygous after phasing, with some individual's phased sequences placed in separate clades, suggesting poor sequence quality or read mapping for these regions in the locus (Pyron et al. 2022). For SNP data (see below), these sites were removed given the heterozygosity filter, and for analyses using full DNA sequences or gene trees, we

filtered these entire loci, retaining 308 sequences. We calculated summary statistics for DNA sequences using the R package ‘PopGenome’ (Pfeifer et al. 2014)

We extracted SNPs using modified functions of the ‘phrynomics’ R package (B. Banbury, <http://github.com/bbanbury/phrynomics>). Datasets with all SNPs, as well as with a single SNP per locus were created. SNPs were required to be parsimony-informative (i.e. found in at least two individuals). Missing data at SNP sites never exceeded 54%, and over 95% of SNPs were represented in at least 90% of individuals, so we retained SNPs with missing data except where noted. SNPs with heterozygosity > 0.75 were removed as these may represent poor sequence quality or departures from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. SNP extraction was then repeated including *P. serratus* as an outgroup species.

Population Structure

To visualize genetic variation among populations, we performed principal components analysis (PCA) on the SNP data using the *glPca* function in the R package ‘adeigenet’ (Jombart 2008). Next, we estimated population structure and admixture using discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) in ‘adeigenet’ (Jombart et al. 2010) and STRUCTURE (Pritchard et al. 2000). For DAPC, k-means clustering was used to identify the most likely number of groups (K) in the data, ranking successive values of K by BIC. Cross-validation was used to select the optimal number of PCs to retain in the analysis, with 500 replicates and a training set of 90% of the data. For STRUCTURE, we used ParallelSTRUCTURE (Besnier and Glover 2013) on the CIPRES Science Gateway (Miller et al. 2011), using one SNP per locus. We explored K values of 1–10, with ten replicate runs of 2×10^6 iterations for each value of K, and the first 500,000 discarded as burn-in. We used the R package ‘pophelper’ (Francis 2017) to

assess the fit of K values using both the log-likelihoods and the Evanno method (Evanno et al. 2005), summarize results across replicate runs and plot results. STRUCTURE was repeated within each of the $K = 5$ genomic groups identified in the first set of analyses (Converse et al. 2015; Janes et al. 2017).

We also performed two spatially-explicit methods to examine the role of isolation-by-distance (IBD) in genetic variation. First, we used the R package ‘conStruct’ (Bradburd et al. 2018), which is analogous to STRUCTURE in estimating admixture proportions in a user-defined number of clusters, but assumes IBD within clusters. Using one SNP per locus, we evaluated values of $K = 1 - 6$ for spatial and non-spatial models using cross-validation, with a 0.6 training proportion and 10 replicates each of 1×10^4 . We used the predictive accuracy to compare different values of K , but because multiple values may provide good solutions (Lawson et al. 2018), we further evaluated results across K values for comparison with our results from STRUCTURE and DACP. Spatial models were fit for $K = 2 - 6$ with 1×10^5 iterations. Next, we used the program FEEMS 1.0.1 in python 3.9.7 to estimate effective migration surfaces (Marcus et al. 2021). FEEMS uses a matrix of genetic distances and the spatial coordinates of populations to estimate effective migration across a spatial graph overlaying the landscape, highlighting areas that have higher or lower migration than expected under an IBD model for the species. Input files were converted from the STRUCTURE input file using PGDspider2 (Lischer and Excoffier 2012) and plink 1.90 (Chang et al. 2015) We created a spatial grid in R by importing a species range from IUCN and adding a 0.15 degree buffer (IUCN 2022). We clipped the western and northern distribution to the extent of our sampling distribution because the full extent of the species range was not sampled in these areas. For FEEMS, we created a spatial grid resolution of size of 8 using ‘dgearthgrid’ function in the R package ‘ddgridR’ (Barnes et al. 2017). For the

smoothness parameter (λ) of FEEMS, which controls the smoothness of the estimated migration surface, we used cross validation to test values from 1×10^{-6} to 10, and we used cross-validation to select the appropriate value.

In our analyses of population structure, as well as tree-based analyses (see below), we identified 10 individuals that exhibited either nuclear admixture between two or more genomic groups (Populations 5, 25, 31, 32, 33, 40, 42, 77, 78), or in one case mitonuclear discordance likely resulting from mitochondrial introgression across a contact zone (Population 79; Fig. 1a,c; Hantak et al. 2019). These admixed samples all occurred at contact zones. We conducted most analyses after excluding admixed samples to better meet the assumptions of analyses that do not account for reticulation; however, for some analyses, we also evaluated the effect of including admixed samples (see below).

Phylogenetic Analyses and Species Delimitation

As a first assessment of the phylogenetic relationships among samples, we used RAxML 8.0 (Stamatakis 2014) to estimate a maximum likelihood phylogeny of concatenated sequence data. Each of the phased alleles at each locus for each individual was arbitrarily assigned to one of two concatenated sequences, such that each individual was represented by two concatenated sequences. With this analysis, each individual's two sequences are expected to be each other's closest relative, with exceptions identifying possible cases of gene flow or incomplete lineage sorting. We used the program 'AMAS' to convert among sequence formats and create a concatenated sequence matrix for RAxML (Borowiec 2016). We assumed a GTR+GAMMA model for each partition (i.e. locus), and assessed node support with 100 rapid bootstrap replicates. *Plethodon serratus* was included as an outgroup. We performed RAxML both

including and excluding our admixed samples. We also estimated a time-calibrated tree using BEAST 2.6.6 (Bouckaert et al. 2019) to estimate divergence times and provide an ultrametric tree for comparative analyses of morphological data; details of the sampling and parameters used for BEAST are included below in the section *Morphological Evolution*.

We used the program ASTRAL v5.7.8 (Zhang et al. 2018) to estimate a species tree of the relationships among the five genomic groups identified by STRUCTURE and DAPC. ASTRAL also calculates the normalized quartet score, the proportion of gene tree quartets that are concordant with the species tree, providing an estimate genealogical discordance. We estimated gene trees for each locus using RAxML 8.0 as input for ASTRAL, assuming a GTR+GAMMA model. Phased alleles of samples were assigned to their genomic group, and admixed samples were excluded. *Plethodon serratus* was included as an outgroup. For branch support, we report both local posterior probabilities and concordance factors.

We estimated support for species within *P. cinereus* using Bayesian Phylogenetics and Phylogeography v4.3.8 (BPP; Rannala and Yang 2017) and the genealogical divergence index (*gdi*; Jackson et al. 2017; Leaché et al. 2019). BPP provides methods for species tree estimation and species delimitation using the multispecies coalescent, while *gdi* is the probability of monophyly under the multispecies coalescent, calculated as a function of population sizes (θ) and divergence times (τ) given a species tree. Higher *gdi* suggests greater genealogical divergence (resulting from a lower θ and/or higher τ), where it has been suggested that values above 0.7 may constitute strong genomic evidence that a lineage is a distinct species, while values below 0.2 are more in line with population-level divergence; values in between are the “gray zone” in which genomic data provide ambiguous support for a group’s species status (Jackson et al. 2017; Leaché et al. 2019). Because BPP is known to conflate intraspecific genetic

structure with distinct species (Sukumaran et al. 2021), an issue exacerbated in widespread and dispersal-limited species, we used the *gdi* as a more conservative approach to quantify the genealogical independence of groups (Leaché et al. 2019).

For BPP and *gdi*, samples were assigned to their respective genomic groups as putative “species”. Analyses were performed with admixed samples included and excluded to evaluate the effect of sampling strategy on the preferred species delimitation inference. In addition, we created a dataset in which we selected a single sample (i.e. locality) that was near the core southeastern portion of the species distribution to represent each group (Group 1: population 1; Group 2: 10; Group 3: 105; Group 4: 36; and Group 5: 100). The single-sample dataset served the dual purpose of matching the sample size of Group 1, for which only one sample was available (it has a limited range), as well as testing how inference is affected when a small sample size is used, due either to a sparse sampling strategy or the biological realities of range-limited species (e.g. montane endemics). For BPP, we estimated the topology of groups and the respective species tree parameters, using models A01 and A00, respectively. In model A01, we used the starting topology estimated by RAxML (Figure 2b): (*P. serratus*; (Group 3; (Group 2; (Group 1; (Group 4; Group 5))))). We assumed a uniform prior over rooted trees. To set the prior distributions of population size (θ) and divergence times (τ), we used ‘PopGenome’ to calculate average per-site nucleotide diversity within groups ($\theta = 0.001$), excluding admixed samples, to inform the inverse gamma prior distribution of θ ($a = 3$; $b = 0.002$), and the average nucleotide diversity distance between each group and the outgroup ($\theta = 0.006$) for the prior distribution of τ ($a = 3$; $b = 0.012$). Locus rates were allowed to vary, with five rate categories. For model A01, we used a MCMC of 100,000 iterations following a burn-in of 10,000 iterations, and a sampling interval of 10 iterations for a total of 10,000 trees sampled from the posterior distribution. Two

replicate runs were performed to ensure convergence of results, and runs were combined and visualized using DensiTree V3.0.2 (Bouckaert 2010). For analysis A00, we used identical methods, with the exceptions that the best tree from analysis A01 was used as the starting tree for the respective dataset in A00, and 100,000 samples were obtained from the posterior distribution. Effective sample sizes >200 for each parameter were verified using Tracer 1.7 (Rambaut et al. 2018).

We then performed a species delimitation analysis in BPP using model A11. This analysis estimates both the topology of the species tree and the number of species in the dataset by sampling trees in which two or more lineages may be collapsed during the MCMC. The posterior distribution thus provides the probability for each possible number of species, from one to a maximum of six in our case including an outgroup. Sampling and parameters were identical to analysis A01, with the addition of algorithm 0 for species delimitation with the epsilon parameter set to 2. The posterior estimates of population sizes (θ) and divergence times (τ) from BPP analysis A00 were used to estimate *gdi* for each group (Leaché et al. 2019). We used R scripts adapted from Leaché et al. (2019) to summarize and plot the distribution of *gdi* values for each group.

Following our initial analyses in BPP and *gdi*, we performed two sets of post-hoc analyses to test the sensitivity of our results that found using a single sample per genomic group yielded higher *gdi* values than the analysis including multiple samples without admixed samples (see results). First, we tested if using an alternative topology for the analysis excluding admixed samples resulted in higher *gdi* values: (*P. serratus*; (Group 3; ((Group 2; Group 1); (Group 4; Group 5)))). The alternate topology did not result in qualitatively different *gdi* values (Supplementary Fig. S19). Second, to verify that that the results of our single-sample *gdi*

analyses were not sensitive to sample selection, we repeated analyses using 10 single-sample datasets in which a random, non-admixed individual was selected to represent each group for BPP and *gdi*. These results suggested that elevated *gdi* values in single-sample datasets were robust to the sample selection (Supplementary Fig. S20).

Our analyses using RAxML, ASTRAL, and BPP assume no gene flow; however, gene flow could be present among local populations or genomic groups due to admixture at contact zones or historical geographic connectivity between groups. To explore the role of gene flow on phylogenetic relationships, we estimated a population tree including migration events using TreeMix (Pickrell and Pritchard 2012). For this analysis, we used all SNPs with no missing data and applied a linkage block size of $k = 50$, exceeding the maximum number of SNPs at any locus. Samples were first treated as individual tips, which has the advantage of reflecting the hierarchical relationships among our geographically structured populations, but includes only a single sample per tip. As with RAxML, TreeMix was performed both including and excluding the admixed samples. We also performed a group-based TreeMix analysis by assigning the samples to their respective genomic group (in this case excluding admixed samples). The R package ‘optM’ (Fitak 2021) was used to evaluate the number of gene flow events to incorporate, comparing the piecewise linear, bent cable, simple exponential, and non-linear least squares models.

We estimated a phylogenetic species network using the program SNaQ in the PhyloNetworks Julia package (Solís-Lemus and Ané 2016; Bezanson et al. 2017; Solís-Lemus et al. 2017). The pseudolikelihood of a given network is derived from expected quartet concordance factors under the coalescent model with reticulation. Observed concordance factors are then used to estimate a species network with a user-defined number of reticulation events.

Gene trees from RAxML were used as input, with phased alleles of all individuals assigned to their genomic group. A starting tree was estimated using ASTRAL-III (Zhang et al. 2018), and we tested models allowing 0 to 5 reticulation events. The group-based analyses in TreeMix and SNaQ (as in ASTRAL and BPP) have the advantage of using multiple samples to estimate the relationships among groups, but they also require *a priori* assignment of samples to groups and involve simplifying assumptions about populations (e.g. panmixia). Therefore, we compared results across analyses to interpret evolutionary history.

Morphological Evolution

We tested if our genomic groups are morphologically divergent, and if climate or post-glacial expansion has influenced morphological evolution in a phylogenetic comparative framework. One of us (EFW) collected morphological data from 935 individuals throughout the sampled range of *P. cinereus* (Supplementary Fig. S1; Supplementary Table S3). Samples were preserved specimens from the Division of Amphibians and Reptiles, at the National Museum of Natural History (Washington D.C., USA). These samples were assigned to a locality included in the AHE dataset, or a sample with mtDNA from Radomski et al. (2020) if AHE data were not available. Morphological samples that were not exact matches to localities with genetic data were in most cases able to be assigned one nearby, which were reasonable approximations of genetic membership (Supplementary Fig. S1), resulting in 33 localities with both genetic and morphological data ($N = 12 - 75$ per locality) (Supplementary Tables S3). The exceptions were samples from eight neighboring sites on the southern Delmarva Peninsula, located between populations 104 and 106. These samples were likely to be members of Group 3, but because their phylogenetic placement was uncertain, we included them in exploratory analyses of trait

variation, but not phylogenetic comparative methods. Morphological measurements included snout-vent length (SVL), total length (TL), body width (BW), head length (HL), trunk length (TRL; length from the first cervical vertebrae to the last sacral vertebrae, equal to SVL – HL), head width (HW; total maximum coronal width of the adductor muscles), elbow-to-shoulder length (ESL), forearm length (FAL), forelimb length (FLL; equal to ESL + FAL), and hindlimb length (HLL). Sex was not determined because not all specimens were easy to sex, but sexual dimorphism in plethodontids tends to be minor in comparison to morphometric differences across lineages (Petranka 1998; Blankers et al. 2012). Individuals with SVL < 32 mm (N = 78) were scored as juveniles (Anthony and Pfungsten 2013) and excluded from analyses, resulting in 835 adult specimens (N = 6 – 75 per locality).

We visualized morphological variation among samples using PCA with the *pcomp* function in R. We included the variables: TRL, HL, BW, HW, ESL, FAL, and HLL. We did not use total length (TL), as the length of the tail varied substantially due to tail breakage. Because all morphological measures were in the same scale (mm), we used the Euclidean variance/covariance matrix for our post hoc tests on the mean centroid values. Samples were grouped by AHE groups, or in the case of admixed samples, the specific admixture combination represented by two or more populations (e.g. “Group 2 & 4”, which included populations 77 and 78; Supplementary Table S2). We performed a PERMANOVA using the *adonis* function in the R package ‘vegan’ to test if group centroids with 95% confidence ellipses were significantly different, using 10,000 replicates (Dixon 2003). After completion of the PERMANOVA, for our post hoc comparison, we used the function *pairwise.perm.manova* from the package ‘RVAideMemoire’, with adjusted *P*-values (p.method = fdr), and a total of 10,000 permutations (Hervé 2018). We performed the PCA and permutation tests once with all body measurements

(excluding composite variables SVL, TL, and FLL), and a second time with trunk length excluded and the remaining measurements divided by SVL to account for differences in overall body size between samples. Body length differs geographically in *P. cinereus* (Highton 1960); therefore, our first analysis incorporates potential body size differences, while the second analysis focused on proportional differences in morphological traits.

We used BEAST 2.6.6 (Bouckaert et al. 2019) to construct a time-calibrated phylogeny, as an ultrametric tree was necessary for PGLS (see below). For 24 localities with morphological data, a sample with genomic data was available in the AHE dataset. For these sites and the remaining 9 localities lacking AHE data, three mtDNA loci were available from prior work: cytochrome-*b* (*Cyt-b*; 1133 bp), the NADH dehydrogenase subunit 2 gene (ND2; 1041 bp), and tryptophan transfer RNA (tRNA^{trp}; 65bp) (Radomski et al. 2020). We created a concatenated DNA sequence matrix of mtDNA and AHE data, in which samples with only mtDNA were provided missing data for the AHE loci. This approach allowed the large number of AHE loci to inform the overall phylogeny while also estimating the placement of samples with only mtDNA data available. The mtDNA and concatenated AHE loci were each given their own partition (two partitions total) for substitution and clock models, and their tree models were linked. HKY+G models were used for each partition (Guillory et al. 2020). We used a relaxed clock (log normal) with clock rates of 6.23×10^{-3} substitutions/Myr for the mtDNA (Kuchta et al. 2016), and 8.99×10^{-4} substitutions/Myr for the AHE partition (Hime et al. 2020). We estimated a tree including all localities with AHE plus the added samples with only mtDNA, as well as a tree dropping admixed samples. Both trees were pruned to samples with morphological data (N = 33 and N = 25 localities, respectively) using the *droptip* function in ‘ape’ R package. For the tree excluding admixed individual, chains were run for 100 million iterations, sampling every 10,000, and we

verified that effective sample sizes (ESS) for all parameters were > 200 . The first 25% of samples were discarded as burn-in. Using the same settings for the analysis including admixed individuals, ESS for several parameters were < 200 . We therefore allowed chains to run longer until stationarity and ESS > 200 were achieved (455,600,000 generations total) and discarded the first 50% of samples as burn-in based on the trace file in Tracer 1.7. For each analysis, we created a maximum clade credibility tree (MCCT) using TreeAnnotator 2.6.0 (Heled and Bouckaert 2013). We verified that our results were similar to the individual-based analyses in RAxML and TreeMix.

We tested the hypothesis that limb reduction is correlated with warmer, drier sites, which other studies have shown is correlated with increased fossoriality (Jockusch 1997). We also tested the hypothesis that that populations having undergone post-glacial range expansion, approximated by higher latitude, exhibit limb elongation, which could be correlated with increased dispersal (Phillips et al. 2006; Pelletier and Carstens 2016). We used phylogenetic generalized least squares regression (PGLS) in the R package ‘caper’ (Orme et al. 2013) to test these hypotheses separately for FLL and HLL. Values for FLL and HLL each represent the average value across individuals from the population. For each of these response variables, we constructed models that included the predictors of mean SVL (to control for body size), latitude, mean annual precipitation, mean annual temperature (WorldClim bioclimate variables at a 30 sec resolution) (Fick and Hijmans 2017) and an interaction effect of precipitation and temperature. Climate data were downloaded using the ‘raster’ (Hijmans et al. 2015) and ‘WorldClimTiles’ R packages (S. Kapitza, available at: <https://github.com/kapitzas/WorldClimTiles>). Before analyses, we verified that predictor variables had correlations $r < 0.7$. All variables were transformed with a natural log transformation to account for the skewed right distribution of the

individual variables. Our measure of phylogenetic signal was estimated for each individual model using maximum likelihood (Orme et al. 2013). We tested for the significance of each predictor variable using the ‘summary’ and ‘anova’ functions in R and then refit models after retaining only predictors that were significant using either method. Effect size was calculated with eta squared (η^2) values for significant predictor variables of latitude, precipitation, or temperature to determine the proportion of the total sum of variance that each individual variable contributed. PGLS was performed both including and excluding admixed populations.

Finally, we performed a “SuperSOM” analysis using the R package ‘delim-SOM’ to combine our morphological data with SNP, spatial (latitude, longitude, and elevation), and climate data (mean annual temperature and precipitation) to estimate the number of population clusters, or candidate species, in a single unsupervised machine learning analysis (Pyron 2023). SuperSOMs allow for multiple data layers to be used to divide a $n \times m$ grid into K distinct clusters. Our morphological data included the same six SVL-corrected morphological variables used in our second PCA analysis above. We used only the samples that had all four data types available ($N = 24$); genomic Group 1 (population 1), was therefore not represented in this analysis. For the SuperSOM, we used a hexagonal grid size of 5×4 , 100 replicates, and 100 steps. We compared values of K and the cluster membership of individual samples, which may be interpreted as “species coefficients” (Pyron 2023). We also evaluated variable importance using codebook vectors following online documentation (<https://github.com/rpyron/delim-SOM>). Support for candidate species was evaluated alongside our other analyses of gene flow and genealogical divergence.

REFERENCES FOR EXTENDED MATERIALS AND METHODS

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